

THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF THE “EUROPEAN GREEN DEAL” AND ITS FINANCIAL ASPECTS

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Annotation

Eng - The European Union is striving to become a global climate power. Following the adoption of the Green Deal, achieving climate neutrality by 2050 has become the motto, goal and pillar of its foreign policy. The internationalization of the Green Deal is planned through a system of foreign policy instruments, including financial instruments, trade policy, border adjustment mechanism, agreements with third countries, development assistance, promotion of EU regulation and standards through cooperation within multilateral institutions, and the construction of a global climate governance system. Currently, regulatory documents and proposals in key areas have been formulated, discussions on the format are ongoing and implementation plans are being developed. In this regard, the analysis of EU initiatives to internationalize the goals of green transformation and the identification of risks and opportunities for cooperation between Uzbekistan and the EU associated with their implementation are relevant. Attention will also be paid to the use of financial and non-financial mechanisms to support the “green” economy and green financing instruments, as well as the process of using the experience of European Union countries in Uzbekistan’s transition to a green economy.

Key words:

❖ *Green Deal, EU, energy transition, renewable energy sources, innovation and digitalization, decarbonization.*

Introduction.

Long-term trends in macroeconomic dynamics are in many ways the determining factor influencing the direction of structural changes in the global financial system. Over the past few decades, an increasing share of influencing factors has been made up of environmental and climatic challenges and tasks, otherwise known as “green”. The increasing role of “green” factors, especially in developed countries, in the late 1960s - early 1970s was caused by the awareness of the degree of underestimation of the impact of human economic activity on the environment,

which could not but affect the pace of technological improvement in production and infrastructure development. In this regard, a kind of parity combination of ever-increasing human needs for improving the quality of life and level of consumption, and the possibilities of production to meet them without significant detrimental impact on the environment arose. In addition, in the mid-1970s, the level of oil prices sharply rose, which led to the need to increase the pace of development of energy efficiency in industrial production, energy-saving technologies, and this was an additional

powerful impetus in favor of increasing the role of the “green” factor.

Green Deal: key to a climate-neutral and sustainable EU

The European Green Deal (EGD) is a package of long-term initiatives of the European Union on climate strategy and a roadmap for reducing carbon emissions by EU countries by 55% by 2030 and achieving carbon neutrality by 2050, which will inevitably require large investments, was announced by the President of the European Commission Ursula von der Leyen in December 2019.

The European Union is introducing increasingly stringent climate and environmental standards for doing business. However, approaches that involve increased levels of (quasi) government intervention to impose a climate-oriented socio-economic transition should not be considered uniquely European. They emerged after the global financial crisis of 2008 in various countries, including the United States and China, as a response to the climate crisis. In this case, intervention is focused on directing public and private capital flows into key sectors for the EU[1].

The EU is talking about encouraging investment strategies by private investors that internalise environmental costs as financial risks – as opposed to externalising such risks, which is the standard principle for most financial strategies. The problems that arise in this regard are addressed through de-risking, securitisation and hedging techniques designed to free up and deploy more private finance and resources. In addition to measures to encourage and channel private investment, the “green transition” includes an accompanying review of European regulations and laws, as well as action plans for key economic sectors. In order to determine the financial sustainability of the European Green Deal, this article places its financial aspects, which are

critical for the success of the EGS as a whole, in a broader political-economic context, including such interdependent categories as the priorities of the EU environmental policy, the relevant political and legal competences of the EU institutions and its role in international cooperation on climate issues, for which, in particular, relevant official documents, including European regulations and decisions of the Council of Ministers, are analyzed. The fact that the EU financial programs now explicitly give priority to the implementation of the climate agenda increases the chances of the success of the EGS. Thus, the intra-European and international sides of the Green Deal are presented here as directly linked.

The COVID-19 pandemic has deeply affected the EU economy, adversely affecting its efficiency. But the unprecedented European response to this crisis, undertaken by Brussels in spring 2020 within the framework of the cohesion policy, such a financial instrument as the NextGenerationEU program, as well as the changes made to the system of the EU's own (budgetary) resources, are also impressive. Taken together, these steps indicate that the European Union, in terms of its finances, is now in principle capable of providing a more impressive response to modern socio-economic challenges, which has taken the form of the Green Deal. Within its framework, Brussels intends to use the funding that has become available to it to the maximum extent possible to implement far-reaching climate goals. According to the Commission's calculations, the implementation of the NextGenerationEU will require 260 billion euros in additional investment annually. However, critics note that, despite the approximate nature of such calculations, the figure is, in principle, understated by at least 40 billion, since it is based on the previous target of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 40% by 2030 from the 1990 level. Increasing the share of renewable energy sources in the energy generation structure will require particularly

large expenditures. It is necessary to finance the electrification of transport, increasing the energy efficiency of buildings and structures, and invest in low-carbon technologies. At the same time, according to statements by environmental NGOs, even the target of 55% is insufficient to keep global warming at acceptable levels.

At the same time, the burden on the EU's public finances could increase in the coming years if the COVID-19 pandemic develops unfavorably, drawing away funds needed to implement the green transition objectives. Reliance on private financial circles could turn out to be a weak point in European plans if, having already invested heavily in the hydrocarbon industry, large investors begin to give preference to short-term profits rather than long-term climate calculations. In any case, it follows from the intentions announced by the EC that, within the framework of the implementation of the Green Deal, measures to stimulate private investment, funds from state budgets (EUR 114 billion) and a significant part of the EU supranational budget will be used to increase its financing, including for guarantee support for private investment carried out through the European Investment Bank. The EIB is designated as the EU's climate bank, which will promote the goals of the Green Deal both in Europe and beyond. From 2021 onwards, all EIB operations must be consistent with the 2015 Paris climate agreement, including the goal of phasing out financing for fossil fuel projects[6].

Investment opportunities and key areas of the European Green Deal

The investment plan contains three directions.

The first direction is to attract at least €1 trillion in sustainable public investment by 2030. Of this amount, €528 billion will come from the EU multiannual budget for 2021–2027, plus revenue from the European Emissions Trading Scheme. The Commission

particularly hopes that “a higher share of climate and environmental spending in the European budget than ever before will help attract more private capital, with the European Investment Bank playing a key role.”

The second direction is activating. We are talking about the intention to provide incentives for unlocking and redistributing both public and (especially) private capital investments. The Action Plan for Stimulating Sustainable Financing is being implemented and the regulations for financial reporting in accordance with its standards have been adopted.

The third area is practical support for government bodies and local authorities, as well as for initiators of “green” projects that are justified from the Commission’s point of view, in their planning, development and implementation.

The main instrument of the Investment Plan is the Just Transition Mechanism (JTM). It is designed to provide priority support to territories and industries that will face particularly serious challenges in the accelerated transition to climate neutrality, and has three supports:

1) a Just Transition Fund of €17.5 billion (€7.5 billion from the EU multiannual budget plus €10 billion from Next Generation EU), primarily for communities and territories that are most affected by its adverse socio-economic impacts;

2) an InvestEU investment programme to mobilise at least €650 billion in long-term public and private investment in 2021–27 for a sustainable recovery of the European economy, of which 30% is earmarked for climate action (it provides funding for innovative initiatives with increased financial risks, backed by an EU budget guarantee of €26.2 billion);

3) Public Sector Loan Facility – a credit line for optimising public financing in target regions, provided through the EIB (here support takes the form of grants from the European Union in combination with loans

from the EIB, and is provided to projects from which no financial return is expected).

As follows from the conclusions of the July 2020 European Council, climate action is now integrated into all policies and programmes financed from the EU budget and the Next Generation EU fund. In addition, all such expenditure must be compatible with the European goals of achieving climate neutrality by 2050, the climate targets for 2030 and not contradict the Paris Agreement and the “no harm” principle reflected in the European Taxonomy Regulation. At the same time, while Next Generation EU initially provided for some funds for international action, in the final version of the agreement of the Member States on this matter, they were completely redirected to solving the Union’s internal tasks[4].

Many of the Green Deal initiatives require new technologies, a transformation of existing financial models and a change in trade channels. Research and development is funded by the Horizon Europe budget programme, through which the EU will form green partnerships between industries and its Member States in areas such as batteries, clean (renewable) hydrogen, low-carbon steel, the built environment and biodiversity. The newly created European Innovation Council has also allocated €300 million from its own budget for “market-creating” innovations that will contribute to the EGD’s objectives.

The Just Transition Fund is subject to climate conditionality: to benefit from it, a country must commit to achieving carbon neutrality by 2050. If a country fails to do so, its receipt of funds from the Fund may be reduced to half of its allocated national share.

The InvestEU scheme provides a loan guarantee from the EU budget to investors investing in locally initiated projects in four areas:

- Sustainable infrastructure (€9.9 billion EU guarantee);
- Research, innovation and digitalisation (€6.6 billion);

- Small and medium-sized enterprises (€6.9 billion);

- Social investment and vocational training (€2.8 billion).

Opportunities for such investment are provided to EU partners (the European Investment Bank Group, the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, national development banks), intending to act directly or through financial intermediaries. To receive European support, the proposed projects must:

- respond to market failures or a lack of capital investment and be economically viable;
- require EU support at the start;
- achieve a multiplier effect as a result and, where possible, attract private investment;
- help achieve EU policy objectives (especially environmental and digitalisation).

Member States may (subject to agreement with the Commission, on a voluntary basis) invest in such projects funds that come to them through the European Structural Funds or the Comprehensive Recovery Plan for Europe. In doing so, they will also be entitled to benefit from the EU budget guarantee with a high credit rating.

The rules of the third pillar of the JTM stipulate that the EU financial partners will invest in the relevant high-risk projects, also relying on the EU credit guarantee (we are talking about investments in public infrastructure, including in the fields of energy and transport, in district heating networks, in efficient waste management, as well as in social infrastructure, including social housing, while support for investments related to fossil fuels is excluded). Upon closer examination, it becomes clearer that a significant part of the promised investments comes from a reshuffling of existing EU funds, while the main hopes are pinned on the mobilization of national funds and private investment.

From a constitutional point of view, Article 3 of the Treaty on European Union established a balance between such general

lines as sustainable development, a high level of environmental protection (supported by the principle of environmental integration in Article 11 of the TFEU), ensuring the smooth functioning of the Single Internal Market and economic growth, and fulfilling social objectives. But in political and legal practice, the EU's course has clearly been tilted towards prioritizing its economic goals. Now, as can be seen, Brussels is clearly striving to consolidate, at least at the technical and administrative level, such an understanding of "sustainable" investment in the process of making its financial decisions, in which the relationship between economic, market and non-economic considerations of the supranational executive power in the EU may be somewhat shifted relative to the previous one, towards greater consideration of the latter. Similar thoughts are suggested, for example, by the important regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council of 2020, which has already entered into force, on the taxonomy (classification) of "green" projects (Taxonomy Regulation), which deals with economic activities that must be assessed as sustainable from an environmental point of view.

The regulation sets out six environmental targets:

- 1) mitigation of the negative impacts of climate change;
- 2) adaptation to climate change;
- 3) sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources;
- 4) transition to a circular economy;
- 5) prevention and control of environmental pollution;
- 6) protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems.

The EC is responsible for drawing up an updated closed list of responsible environmental actions on this basis. It is also empowered to adopt delegated acts and implementing acts specifying how competent authorities and market participants must

comply with the mandatory requirements set out in the regulation[5].

The Green Deal reflects the EU's commitment to achieving carbon neutrality by 2050, thereby adjusting its own economic growth trajectory, as a regional contribution to the 2015 Paris Agreement on climate change and the UN Sustainable Development Goals. As the research conducted here confirms, Brussels is likely to pursue this goal persistently and systematically within its own borders, for which it will ultimately be able to mobilise significant financial resources. In this sense, it is encouraging for Brussels that global private financing for green goals is growing at an impressive rate every year.

For its part, the European Commission successfully issued its own green bonds for the first time on 12 October 2021. By the end of 2026, it intends to issue green bonds on behalf of the European Union in a total volume of 250 billion euros. The mechanism for their operation is designed to ensure that the funds raised are directed towards green projects within the integration association, with the EC reporting on their impact on the environment[7]. Among other things, acting in cooperation with international partners and at multilateral venues, Brussels also intends to consistently promote the "external dimension" of the Green Deal, relying on its exceptional market and regulatory power. The reduction in European demand for fossil fuels, along with the growing demand for cobalt, nickel and other mineral raw materials critical for the energy transition, will have a strong impact on global markets and, as a result, on the economies of countries rich in oil and minerals.

The European Union justifies its plans to introduce a cross-border carbon tax (Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism, CBAM), which will be levied on goods imported into the European Union depending on the volume of greenhouse gas emissions during their production, by low decarbonization ambitions in other regions of the world, which need to be

somehow spurred[3]. According to the European Commission, as a supplement to the European emissions trading scheme, it should put local carbon-intensive products on the European market (initially, we are talking about aluminum, cement, iron/steel, as well as electricity and fertilizers) in comparable competitive conditions with imported products, if the production of the latter is not burdened in the country of production with comparable costs for “green” transit. The corresponding legislative proposal was put forward by the EC in July 2021, but this is an idea that has been maturing for quite a long time.

In 1992, the EC proposed that the EU introduce its own carbon tax to limit CO₂ emissions and lead international coordination on this issue. The EU’s specific interest in international tax coordination stems from the comparatively higher level of taxation in Europe, which undermines its position in global competition[10]. However, in 2001, the corresponding legislative initiative was withdrawn after encountering strong resistance from a number of member states and business lobbyists. In the 1990s, during the negotiations on the Kyoto Protocol, the EU initially preferred a tax rather than the emissions trading system that subsequently emerged in Europe (the latter option was then more actively supported by the United States).

By 2009, carbon taxes were again a topic of discussion within an integrated Europe, but agreement among member states remained elusive, although environmental taxation had gradually become an important source of public financial resources. In 2010, the EC considered implementing a minimum pan-European tax in the form of pollution permits purchased under the EU ETS (introduced in 2005), where the new tax would be calculated in carbon equivalent. But this proposal did not pass at that time: the EU’s material interests came into conflict with the interests of energy resource exporters, which is what we are actually seeing

today[9]. The idea behind the new tax is that imported products with a carbon intensity exceeding European emissions standards would be taxed at the EU border at a rate determined by the EU’s own emissions trading system, but this adjustment would be offset by carbon taxation in the country of origin of the imports – though only if that country reaches an agreement with the European Commission.

With the help of CBAM, Brussels hopes to avoid the relocation of energy-intensive production (carbon leakage): to ensure that the production of such goods does not leave the EU countries for third countries, which could similarly benefit from their less stringent climate policy than Europe. The carbon footprint and tax base reporting mechanism, which imposes a significant administrative burden on importers to the EU countries, is planned to be launched on January 1, 2023, and from the beginning of 2026, CBAM will come into full force. Then importers will have to purchase digital certificates allowing them to import products into the EU Single Internal Market, which will reflect the carbon footprint of imported goods. It is likely that by that time the list of imported products covered by it will be expanded. The EU is set to base the price of emission permits on the average price of weekly auctioned emissions permits on the European carbon market, which most analysts expect to continue to rise until 2030 (it is currently around €60 per tonne of carbon).

During the transition period, emissions from the relevant imports will have to be reported. The emissions charge will be introduced and will increase in stages from 2026 to 2035. During this time, certain EU producers will lose 10% of the free emission allowances they previously received under the EU scheme. The Commission hopes that this approach is consistent with WTO rules, avoiding “double protection” for European producers[8]. But it also means that even by 2030, the free allowances for the relevant sectors within the EU will only be halved, while

the Commission intends to subject European households to a full carbon charge several years earlier. If importers can prove, based on data from import producers, that the carbon price has already been paid during the production of the import, the corresponding amount will be deducted from the value of the European certificate.

There are currently more than 60 national carbon pricing instruments in use around the world, including in China and individual US states including California, such as cap-and-trade schemes or taxes, which are not mutually exclusive. According to the World Bank, they cover about 20% of global greenhouse gas emissions.

Conclusion.

To sum it up, we can conclude that in the current reality it is impossible to ignore environmental and climate problems, this understanding occurs both at the national and international levels, and concerns almost every inhabitant of the planet. One of the most important areas of improving the human environment is the transition to a “green” economy. When implementing this transition, it is implied that “green” financial instruments are used. But such global transitions are always accompanied by many problems that require solutions both at the international and national levels.

It is obvious that the old methods of economic regulation no longer work, the monetary policy of quantitative easing no longer leads to the expected results, inflation in many countries is steadily growing. The global energy crisis that broke out in October 2021 once again makes it clear that the processes of

“green” energy transition must be sustainable but smooth, otherwise there is always a risk of getting a completely unexpected negative result.

The EU should set an example for others regarding the potential socio-economic consequences of decarbonization. As a leader in global efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, the EU will be among the first to face their consequences in the socio-economic sphere. The goal of the EU Green Deal is to sensibly advance the reduction of the carbon intensity of the economy, minimizing the negative effects of industrial transformation and ensuring maximum social inclusiveness of the process. Issues of a just transition, as well as the redistributive effect of climate policy, are key in the process of reducing carbon intensity. In addition, green industrial policy and green investment are key policy areas to maximize the benefits of decarbonization, while creating jobs and ensuring economic growth. The EU could create multilateral forms and platforms for exchanging experiences and best practices with international partners. Such platforms could help replicate the EU's experience for partners in carbon markets, which, for example, made a significant contribution to the launch of national emissions trading in China.

Together, these pillars would support EU foreign policy in promoting the Green Deal. They take into account the geopolitical challenges that other countries are likely to face in implementing the deal and as a result of climate change, and they offer ways to extend the EU's decarbonisation efforts beyond its borders, thereby increasing the chances of the Green Deal itself being successful.

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